

COORDINATION OF THE PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS AND THE CHOICE OF THE RIGHT TEACHING METHODS - AN IMPORTANT ASPECT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF EDUCATION AND UPBRINGING

Abdijabbar Norbutayevich Usmanov

Associate Professor of Primary Education Methodology, JSPI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7541557>

Abstract. *This article describes the theoretical and practical problems facing the education system, the importance of coordinating the pedagogical process and the right choice of teaching methods in overcoming them to ensure the effectiveness and prospects of education.*

Keywords: *process, coordination, teaching, selection, education, problem, efficiency, perspective, essence, provision.*

The high efficiency of education and upbringing of the continuing education system in many ways requires the implementation of important tasks such as the appropriacy (optimization) of the pedagogical process and the correct selection of teaching methods (styles).

Pedagogical process is very complex, and its coordination requires taking into account many scientists, including: what part of the day the lesson takes place; whether the student's brain is not tired in the first hours or in the last hours; what is the complexity of the subject matter; the role of students in the formation of independent knowledge of this topic and many factors.

Therefore, the teacher should always face the following problems.

1. Why does a lesson go differently?
2. Why are the results of the lessons different?
3. Why does a particular lesson excel in one learning group and fail in another?

Even in different lessons of the teacher, students behave differently, they become unrecognizable, like different people.

A lesson is creativity, but creativity is creativity not only for the teacher, but also for the student. A teenager's lack of active participation in the lesson will lead to a failure of the lesson. No matter how much the teacher works in the lesson, without the participation of the students he is isolated in the lesson and teaches to himself.

The quality and effectiveness of the lesson does not depend on a multi-page structured lesson plan. Although the goals, tasks to be carried out, who will do, what and when, the time of each action are divided into seconds in the plan, no matter how much effort and time is spent on preparing for the lesson, it is possible to be not satisfied with the lesson and not to achieve the intended goal. Sometimes a well-crafted lesson plan can become overwhelming, and the teacher can seem like he's teaching in an empty classroom.

The teaching process is very complicated, and the teacher has to consider many factors. In this sense, each teacher should have the following pedagogical qualities to ensure the effectiveness of coordination of this process.

An important task in this process is to organize the teacher's preliminary preparation correctly and appropriately. This ensures that the essence of the above pedagogical qualities is correctly understood. Below are brief descriptions of the essence of these concepts.

Thoroughness: it is considered the most important factor in the pedagogical process, in which it is necessary to observe the events of the lesson process not with the naked eye, but with deep attention, to pay attention to the fact that even "insignificant mistakes" can lead to great success or ineffectiveness; refers to the questions to this situation and event - why so? what to do?

A critical look: It involves looking critically at observable bad situations, looking for the cause of the negative consequences, and trying to identify the causes and consequences of what needs to be done in order to find the answer to the question why.

Imagination: trying to logically imagine the reasons for what should be done and the ways of its implementation. Involves, imaginary experiments imagining and comparing solutions to problems in different ways.

Knowledge: in the pedagogical process, as in any creativity, imagination begins with the emergence of an idea to find a solution to a problem. An idea is a bud of knowledge. A person without a certain amount of knowledge cannot have any imagination or breakthrough idea no matter how hard he tries. The proverb " One is won with a good wrist – thousand are won with a good knowledge" is not said in vain.

Interest in learning: it is not enough for any professional to know only his field, but it is necessary to know other fields as well in the pedagogical process. For this, it is necessary to have an interest in learning. Only then will it be easy to solve the problem. What is the difference between a pedagogue who only repeats information from textbooks and a parrot?

Desire: Although desire in the pedagogical process is similar to interest in knowledge, they should not be confused with each other. Desire is, in general, dedication and enthusiasm to eliminate the negative situation associated with an event, situation, condition and its consequences. As in other fields, in the pedagogical process, positive qualities such as great enthusiasm, desire and will to do one's work are necessary. Vipers who do not have these qualities can be compared to beggars carrying someone else's child.

Voluntary: is to resolutely overcome mental, spiritual, physical and other organizational difficulties in the way of the realization of the goal. Voluntary action is complex, and to achieve it, it is necessary to go through a series of steps. In it, mental processes such as attention, thoroughness, perception, thinking, imagination, reflection, memory take a certain direction and appear consciously under the influence of volitional effort, enthusiasm. Execution plays a crucial role in the stages of volition. No other force can accomplish such a task. Unwilling pedagogues can be compared to birds looking for grain in search of dung, as mentioned in the essence of Navoi's wisdom.

Mental readiness: to achieve constant readiness in any situations where mental and physical effort is required. Mental work is not visible, it is much harder than the work of those who create material wealth with physical work, because mental work creates spiritual wealth, exhausts the brain, quickly tires a person, and the result is not always as expected. The Arab saying "Even if you tire your body, don't tire your mind" is not said for nothing. For the development of mental readiness, "chain links" such as health, patience, tolerance, good character, financial security, peaceful family life, working in an intellectual team are necessary. The following teaching methods are widely used in the pedagogical process:

1. Oral method of teaching (consists of such methods as lecture, conversation, story);
2. Demonstration methods of teaching - consists of methods of the use of demonstration, improvement, coordination, selection of conditions.
3. Practical method of teaching (consists of methods of using, improving, and developing practical tasks)
4. The problem-search method of teaching (consists of ways of creating a problem situation, the connection of oral, visual and practical methods, appropriate recommendations)
5. Critical method of teaching (consists of methods of defining inductive, deductive and other logical bases, selecting and applying important ones)
6. The method of independent work of teaching (consists of methods of choosing independent work, different approaches to independent work, forming important conditions for improvement)
7. The method of encouraging and justifying students' activities (consists of methods of forming their interest in knowledge, correctly assessing their duties and religious responsibilities)
8. Control method in teaching (consists of oral and written, laboratory-practical, computer control methods)

Coordination of the above-mentioned pedagogical process, in turn, requires the correct choice of teaching methods. At this point, it is necessary to correctly interpret the meaning of the terms "way" (method) and "style" (methodology).

“Way” can be compared with the russian term “способ” and it came to us as an integrated word.

The word “style” have come from greek word “stulos”, it means "stick", which was used by the ancient Greeks for writing letters. That is, it means the method of using a stick when writing a letter.

“Style” can be referred to russian “стиль” (“слог”). [1] Besides, in sports “style” (in wrestling) often has a meaning of “technique”, in the military - "tactics", "maneuver". For example, when explaining sewing, dressing or singing of a performer in western “style”, it is said

explaining sewing, dressing or singing of a performer in European “manner”. Also, when comparing the sewing of Kokand and Andijan doppy, the first one is said to be sewn in Kokand "style" and the second one in Andijan "style". In this sense, "style" is used to describe the final result of a sample of creativity, its form, content, color, embroidery and other specific scientific features in a broader sense, and this, in turn, is also used in the pedagogical process. Regardless of which "style" it is made in, considering that the process of sewing the above doppy consists of several specific "methods" and operations, it means that "style" is a set of "methods". In other forms of creativity, "style" means the sum of "technique" and "maneuver".

In particular, "Soviet encyclopedic dictionary" in the 1980 edition interprets methodology not as a way to achieve any goal, but as a set of methods or operations of practical or theoretical mastering (knowledge) of reality.

Coordinating the pedagogical process and choosing teaching methods from a psychological point of view is an intellectual-volitional act of accepting and implementing more effective solutions to certain educational tasks, which requires accepting pedagogical tasks before making a decision (for example, tasks of choosing the most appropriate teaching method for this class); the presence of several possible ways of solving the given task; understanding the need to choose the most suitable combination of them for these conditions; getting acquainted with information on the comparative effectiveness of possible methods of solving similar tasks; reducing the number of possible options for connecting methods to two as much as possible; comparing their effectiveness and expected time consumption; selecting one option from a combination of styles that best matches the coordination criterion. All of the above is directly related to the behavior of the pedagogue who, relying on general pedagogical recommendations, concretizes his activity taking into account existing situations.

The criterion for coordination of the pedagogical process is: firstly, to achieve the educational results that correspond to the set goals and the specific educational opportunities of all students, and to observe the hygienic norms of the time spent on doing homework.

If these two criteria are followed when choosing teaching methods, then such a choice can be recognized as appropriate.

The idea of a suitable combination of styles is always concrete. What is successful and effective for some conditions may be completely inappropriate for other conditions, another topic. The suitability of this or that style is not explained by its name and the fact that it has become a habit. Appropriately chosen methods allow enough time to solve the assigned tasks as desired. That is why it is possible to solve the tasks of education and upbringing successfully and appropriately with respect to various combinations of methods. Adherence to the standard in choosing the appropriate option does not allow to go blindly towards the use of all teaching methods in each situation, but requires to find the appropriate standard of combining methods for the relevant conditions.

In this sense, the basis of appropriate selection is systematic clarification, generalization and standard.

Since the use of teaching methods depends on a concrete pedagogical process, it is impossible to calculate the constant weight of each method in the educational process, to set a certain percentage for demonstrativeness, difficulty, etc. In short, in every pedagogical situation, it is necessary to choose the teaching methods not by default, but by understanding and in a clear way. Choosing teaching methods is determined by:

1. The laws of teaching and the principles arising from it;
2. The goals and objectives of education in general and at this stage in particular;
3. The content and methods of this science in general, generally and particularly with this subject, topic in particular;
4. Educational opportunities of students:
 - a) age (physical, mental capabilities);
 - b) level of preparation (educational and upbringing opportunities);
 - c) with the characteristics of the class team.
5. The characteristics of external conditions (geographic, production, etc.);
6. Pupils' capabilities: their previous experiences, certain combinations of styles, knowledge of typical situations of a more effective pedagogical process, the level of their theoretical and practical readiness, the ability to use certain methods and tools, the skills of choosing appropriate options, personal qualities and so on.

Such a group of requirements is determined by the approach directed to all the main elements of a system of requirements: students, teachers, external conditions, as well as components of the teaching process - the purpose, content, methods, forms, means and expected results of teaching.

The choice of teaching methods should be subordinated to the laws of teaching and the problems arising from them, these methods should be used to comprehensively solve the tasks of education, upbringing and maturation; to ensure the scientificity of the methods used; specifies the need to focus on their convenience for students, the development of activity and independence in learning, and ensuring the strength of knowledge, skills and qualifications.

Understanding the possibilities of each of the teaching methods saves the pedagogues from the template in teaching and copying from one to the other, and leads to the choice of appropriate methods for the relevant situation.

Due to the fact that teaching tasks are carried out through its specific content, teaching methods should take into account the nature of the educational material and the character of the students' actions necessary for mastering that content.

From this, there is a criterion between the compatibility of the methods with the characteristics of the teaching content. If we assume that style is defined as content and form of movement, then the importance of the criterion becomes clearer. Because one content can be better revealed by inductive, another – by deductive method; one content is easy to search and learn, while another does not allow to use such a method, and so on.

In modern pedagogy and psychology, the events that cause student failure are divided into the following main groups.

Internal:

1. shortcomings in personal education (in the development of personal moral qualities; in the attitude of a person towards teachers, community, family, etc.; in labor education).
2. Defects in mental development of the person (slow development of the intellect, will of the person, lack of emotional spheres of the person, interest in knowledge).
3. Deficiencies in biological development (deficiencies in sensory organs, physical weakness, features of higher nervous activity that negatively affect the student, psychotopological changes).

4. Deficiencies in a person's learning experience (deficiencies in knowledge and special skills, academic work skills).

External:

1. Shortcomings in school influence (in the teaching process, individual approach to the student; in the educational influence of the school - teachers, student group, etc.).
2. Disadvantages under the influence of the environment outside the school (family, peers at school, children and adults at home).

Only after teachers know the exact scope of the causes of non-learning, they can correctly determine the methods of their elimination and prevention of any unpleasantness.

Some basic requirements for the appropriate selection of teaching methods can be expressed in advance as follows.

1. First of all, it is necessary to ensure the selection of the system of methods of mastering a new subject in advance.
2. Determining the leading method of learning new material, taking into account the nature of the lesson tasks and the content of the educational material, according to the place of this lesson in the system of lessons.

Applying this method with various teaching methods in the system of lessons in order to ensure the activities of students with different types of memory, attention, motivation, attitude to learning.

3. It is necessary to use and deepen the methods that require students to show more independence and activity in order to increase the real opportunities of students. It is not possible to specify a default set of methods for a class. As the class capacity increases, you should also consider updating the methods.
4. After that, it is necessary to clarify the choice of methods, taking into account the capabilities of students and the teacher, first of all, the level of educational readiness and attitude of the student group.
5. When choosing teaching methods, preference should be given to methods that can maximally demonstrate the strengths of the teacher in his individual pedagogical technique.
6. During teaching, it is necessary to take into account changes in the situation and make adjustments in accordance with the choice of methods in order to ensure the constant preservation of the resonance of methods and class possibilities.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the main issue in coordinating the pedagogical process and choosing the right teaching methods is to achieve the adoption of the most optimal and effective solutions in pedagogical activity. Selection of the appropriate teaching process and teaching methods can only be done using a dialectical systemic approach that requires their manifestation in legitimate interaction. This implies a pedagogical process equivalent to the concepts of innovation, creativity, and competence. This process includes three directions and they are:

1. pedagogical neology (Greek neo - new and logos - education, teaching about innovation) is a process of studying and summarizing all innovations in the field of pedagogy;
2. pedagogical axiology (Greek axiom - to respect, unprovable doctrine) is the process of selecting the most effective pedagogical innovations;

3. pedagogical praxology (from the Greek prax - action and logos - teaching, teaching about practical application) - this process involves the practical application of selected pedagogical innovations.

Only with fine coordination of pedagogical processes associated with the coordination of the above-mentioned pedagogical process, pedagogical activity can gracefully and objectively convey to ordinary students those successes or lags that they did not see (or saw with difficulty) as quickly and deeply as a ray of light, and can impress pupils (students) as if they were talking with a saint, and lead them to a bright life.

Pedagogical process is an educational process in which goal-oriented interaction of participants obeying the laws of pedagogy takes place.

Coordination is a pedagogical technology that takes into account all the influencing factors of the environment in education, upbringing and development.

Methods are the basis of didactic principles of building and implementing of not putting too much "burden" on students in education, consciously mastering that these burdens are not a disease, but a symptom of it, achieving prevention of "disease" by developing the ability to analyze, think, and imagine.

Today's urgent problem facing the continuous education system of our republic is to achieve coordination of the above three interactions of the pedagogical process. This, in turn, provides an appropriate pedagogical process based on the regulation of the continuous education system, the development of management documents and its implementation, and serves as an important perspective for the development of the heirs of our great future.

REFERENCES

1. Ushinskiy K.D. Tanlangan pedagogik asarlar, Moskva., 1974, 1-tom, 21-22-betlar.
2. X.Tog'ayev., N.Alimov. Bo'lajak agromuhandis pedagoglarning texnik ijodkorligini rivojlamtirish. "Xalq ta'limi". 2002-yil 4-son 36-38-betlar.
3. O'zbekiston Respublikasining "Ta'lim to'g'risida"gi qonunlari, 1997-yil 29-avgust
4. O'zbek – Sovet ensiklopediyasi. 12-tom. 1979-yil, 17-18-bet
5. Sovet ensiklopedik lug'ati. 1980-yil
6. Usmanov, A. (2021). BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLAR O'QUVCHILARIGA QAMBAR OTA IJODINI O'RGATISH USULLARI. Boshlang'ich ta'limda innovatsiyalar, (Dekabr).
7. Usmanov, A. (2021). Glaballashuv davrida fonema: Glaballashuv davrida fonema. Boshlang'ich ta'limda innovatsiyalar.
8. Ю.К.Бабенский. Hozirgi zamon umumiy ta'lim maktabida o'qitish metodikasi. Toshkent, "O'qituvchi" 1988-yil, 49-55-betlar.
9. Sh.Sharipov. Ta'lim jarayonida yangi pedagogik texnologiyalar. Xalq ta'limi. №1, 2003-yil, 104-106-betlar
10. Sh. Atabayev (2022). Boshlang'ich ta'lim ona tili va o'qish savodxonligi mashg'ulotlarida savol-topshiriqlar ustida ishlash-tadqiqot ob'ekti sifatida. Science and innovation, 1 (B7), 1077-1080. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7295409
11. Usmanov, A. (2021). Glaballashuv davrida fonema: Glaballashuv davrida fonema. Boshlang'ich ta'limda innovatsiyalar.